

The Effect of Health Education with a Pop-Up Book Media about Menarche on the Female Teenagers's Knowledge in SDN (Public Elementary School) 008 Samarinda Seberang 2018

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Abstract— Background: The Menarche is the first menstruation for a woman when a woman onset in the period of puberty. Based on study of preliminary in the SDN 008 Samarinda Seberang as many as 11 in 67 female students of the 6th grade have experienced menstrual said didn't know about the menarche and expressed fear, shock, and confused as to what it will do when it gets first time menstruation. **Objective:** This research aims to analyze the effect of health education with a pop-up book media about menarche in the female teenagers's knowledge in SDN 008 Samarinda Seberang. **Method:** This research was a pra experiment with one group pretest and posttest design. The sample consist of 36 female teenagers taken by Cluster Random Sampling and Simple Random Sampling. Technique of collecting data was done by distributing questionnaire to the respondent. Technique of analyzing data included univariate analysis and bivariate analysis using Paired T-test. **Result:** The result showed there was significant effect of health education on the respondent's knowledge, with p value = 0,000 < α (0,05). Its showed there was significant difference of female teenagers's knowledge before and after given health education with pop-up book media. **Conclusion:** Based on the result research, it was recommended for the headmaster to work together with the community health center in providing information on reproductive health to increase female students's knowledge about menarche.

Keywords— Health Education, Knowledge, Menarche.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to WHO (2014) in the DATIN adolescent info it is estimated that adolescent groups in the world numbered 1.2 billion or 18% of the world's population. The total age group of 10-19 years in Indonesia according to the 2010 population census of 43.5 million people or about 18% of the population of Indonesia. According to the Population and Planning Agency (BKKBN), the age range of teenagers is 10-24 years and not yet married. In East Kalimantan (BPS, 2010a) stated that the female population at the age of 10-24 years was 456 thousand people, in Kota Samarinda (BPS, 2010b) as many as 98 thousand people.

Menarche or first menstruation is a sign of puberty in women. Early menstruation occurs at the age of 11-16 years. (Proverawati and Misaroh, 2009). Based on the results of the Basic Health Research (RISKESDAS) the average age of menarche in women in Indonesia is 13 years with an earlier occurrence at less than 9 years of age (Ministry of Health, 2010).

During this time some people are taboo to talk about menstrual problems in the family, so that early adolescents lack sufficient knowledge and good attitudes about physical and psychological changes related to menarche. Many girls don't have the right understanding that menstruation is a normal biological process. They just knew him the first time he experienced menstruation. This is compounded by the fact that girls often have difficulty buying or getting pads when

needed. A UNICEF study in Indonesia in 2015 found that 1 out of 6 girls were forced to go to school for one or more days, during menstruation (Ministry of Health Republic of Indonesia, 2017).

Lack of knowledge about menstruation in young women will have an impact on readiness or unpreparedness in the face of menarche so that it can cause positive reactions and negative reactions during menstruation. Based on the results of research conducted by Pakaya (2017) on "The Relationship between the Role of Parents and Children's Readiness in Facing Menarche in SMP Negeri 21 Samarinda in 2017". The results show that nearly half of the students of SMPN 21 Samarinda, 58 students (49.2%) were not ready to face their first menstruation.

Efforts to reduce unpreparedness in young women when menarche are the role of parents, school teachers or related parties to provide health education or correct information about the changing conditions of adolescents, especially information about menarche. Providing health education is a solution that is highly recommended to overcome this. It will be difficult for adolescents to face menstruation first if they have never known or talked about it (Andriani, 2012).

According to research conducted by Ariesta (2012) with the title "Effects of Health Education on Menstruation on Adolescent Girls' Knowledge in Facing Menarche". It was concluded that there was an increase in knowledge after getting health education for young women in the face of menarche.

Health education in the process is not directly delivered but uses media assistance. Good health education media are media that are able to provide health information or messages in accordance with the level of acceptance of the target, so that the target is willing and able to change behavior in accordance with the message delivered. Through correct information, it is expected that adolescents have attitudes and behaviors that are responsible for their reproductive processes.

The choice of media and methods in the delivery of health education also influences the attractiveness and ease of respondents in understanding the material so that it makes it easy for respondents to capture and understand the material presented and is easy to remember the material. This makes the respondent understand what is meant by the researcher. Media can be divided into two-dimensional media and three-dimensional media. One of the three-dimensional media is Pop-Up Book. With this Pop-Up Book media it is able to form beautiful objects or give amazing effects (Dzuanda, 2011).

From a preliminary study conducted on October 16, 2017 at SDN 008 Samarinda Seberang, it was found that as many as 11 out of 67 grade VI students did not know about menarche and they expressed fear, surprise, and confusion about what they would do when they had their first menstruation. When menstruation occurs they are embarrassed to tell their classmates.

The reason for using this school is because the school has never received health education, especially regarding adolescent reproductive health. Based on the problem above, the writer is interested in conducting research on "The Effect of Health Education with Pop-Up Book Media on Menarche on Adolescent Girls' Knowledge at SDN 008 Samarinda Across 2018"

II. METHOD

This study uses quantitative research types, namely Pre-Experiment, using the design of The One Group Pre-test Post-test Design. The research was conducted at 008 Samarinda Seberang Elementary School in February-March 2018.

The population in this study were all students of class VI SDN 008 Samarinda totaling 384 people, and the sample in this study was grade 6 students who had not had menstruation. Samples taken from this study used cluster random sampling so that 36 people were obtained with the number of samples that had been added by 10%. The variables in this study were divided into two categories, the independent variable was health education with pop-up book media about menarche and the dependent variable was the knowledge of young women about menarche.

The instrument used in this study was a questionnaire. The questionnaire has been structured and made by the researcher himself based on theoretical concepts with a total of 19 statements using the Gutmann scale. Before the questionnaire was given to respondents, the questionnaire was tested for validity and reliability first. The validity and reliability tests were carried out 25, 17 and 20 students at SDN 016, 002 and 001 Samarinda Seberang.

Implementation of data analysis using a computer program. In univariate analysis conducted to analyze each

research variable descriptively by calculating the frequency distribution and percentage, for bivariable analysis using the Paired T-Test formula.

III. RESULTS

The Results of Analysis Univariate

1. The Young Women's Level of Knowledge of Dance Before Being Given Health Education at SDN 008 Samarinda Across The 2018

TABLE I. Distribution of Respondents frequencies based on Young Women Knowledge of tower before Health Education

Variable	Category	F	Percentage (%)
Knowledge Before Health Education	Good	1	2.9
	Enough	26	74.3
	Less	8	22.9
Total		35	100

Source: Primary Data 2018

Based on table I. shows that in the knowledge variable, before being given health education knowledge that most of the young women about menarche in the sufficient category is 26 respondents (74.3%), and 1 respondent (2.9%) in the good category.

2. Level of Knowledge of Young Women About Menarche After Being Given Health Education in SDN 008 Samarinda Across 2018

TABLE II. Distribution of Frequency of Respondents Based on Young Women Knowledge about Menarche after Providing Health Education

Variable	Category	F	Percentage (%)
Knowledge After Health Education	Good	30	85.7
	Enough	4	11.4
	Less	1	2.9
Total		35	100

Source: Primary Data 2018

Based on table II. shows that in the knowledge variable after being given health education there was an increase where almost all the knowledge of young women in the good category was 30 respondents (86.7%) and only 1 respondent (2.9%) was in the poor category.

Bivariate Analysis Results

3. The Effect of Health Education with Pop-up Book Media on Menarche on Adolescent Girls' Knowledge at SDN 008 Samarinda in 2018

TABLE III. Effects of Health Education with Pop-up Book Media on Menarche on Adolescent Girls' Knowledge at SDN 008 Samarinda in 2018

		Knowledge After Being Given Penkes			Total	p
		Good	Enough	Less		
Knowledge Before Given by Penkes	Good	1	0	0	1	0,000
	Enough	24	2	0	26	
	Less	5	2	1	8	
Total		30	4	1	35	

Source: Primary Data 2018

Based on table III. shows that the p value of the Paired T-test is 0,000 which in this study the value of the significance test p value <0.05, it can be concluded that there are significant differences in the knowledge of young women in SDN 008 Samarinda Seberang about menarche before and after being given health education.

IV. DISCUSSION

1. *Young Women Knowledge About Menarche Before Health Education*

Based on the result data before being given health education from 35 respondents, most of them are in the sufficient category, namely 26 respondents (74.3%), and only 1 respondent (2.9%) in the good category.

Adequate knowledge of young women about menarche is due to information that has been received by adolescents about menarche through science learning about puberty in adolescents at school. In addition, cultural factors also influence the experience of mothers, especially young women, about their first menstruation so that the insight of young girls increases.

This is in accordance with the theory proposed by Mubarak (2012) that a person's knowledge is influenced by information, interests and culture. Sufficient knowledge is also in accordance with Diyastuti's research (2015) that the highest level of knowledge of class VI students about Menarche in SDN 3 Plosorejo is in the sufficient category of 18 students (60%).

Student knowledge about menarche can affect student anxiety in the face of the first menstruation. This is in line with Arda's research (2016) that there is a significant relationship between knowledge and the level of anxiety in respondents facing menarche. It was also strengthened by research conducted by Prastantri (2016) that most girls in SDN 3 Bantul experienced mild anxiety levels (52.8%) with a good level of knowledge (50%).

The existence of health promotion is to increase one's knowledge, one of which is by providing health education about menarche to young women so that there is a transfer of information to young women who can increase knowledge. After getting health education about menarche, it is hoped that it can relieve anxiety so that Ramaja's readiness in facing the first menstruation occurs.

This is consistent with research conducted by Sudjana (2015) which states that the majority (72.4%) of VII grade junior high school students have mild anxiety after being given health education about menarche. In addition, a study conducted by Winarti (2017) stated that in the intervention group after being given health education the level of anxiety decreased as seen from the pretest score in the category of severe anxiety of 6 respondents (40%) after the posttest became 2 respondents (13.3%).

Then conducted health education about menarche which according to researchers is the most effective way to increase the knowledge of young women, increasing knowledge by young women about menarche is influenced by information provided by researchers and the environment in schools and the environment around the home.

2. *Young Women Knowledge About Menarche After being given Health Education*

Based on research conducted on respondents, it was found that almost all respondents in the good category were 30

respondents (85.7%), and only 1 respondent (2.9%) was in the poor category.

There was an increase in knowledge in the category of good before the health ministry ie respondents (2.9%) to 30 respondents (85.7%). It can be interpreted that there is a change of knowledge from less categories or good enough categories. These results are also similar to Ariesta's study (2012) with the title "Effects of Health Education on Menstruation on Adolescent Girls' Knowledge in Facing Menarche in SDN 01" that there was a change in the level of knowledge in the intervention group from the majority of the categories to be quite good (62.1%).

This increase in respondents' knowledge shows that health education provided to respondents is acceptable. This is in accordance with the theory of Notoatmodjo (2007) which states that, health education is a learning process for individuals, groups or communities from those who do not know to know, from not being able to do to being able to do it. Particularly in this research is for young women who initially did not know about menarche become aware after being given health education.

The pre test and post test are 15 days apart. This is in accordance with Notoatmodjo (2007) which states that ideally the distance between pre-test and post-test is 15-30 days. If the time interval is too short, chances are the respondent still remembers the first test questions. Whereas if the time interval is too long, it is likely that the respondent has changed in the variable to be measured.

Research that conducted pre-test and post-test with a time interval of 15 days after health education was conducted by Ariesta (2012) and also conducted by Harnawati (2014) with the title "The Effect of Adolescent Reproductive Health Counseling on Dating Attitudes of Class XI Students in SMKN I Sewon Bantul Yogyakarta in 2014 ". From both studies it can be concluded that there was an increase in knowledge 15 days after being given health education.

3. *Effect of Health Education with Pop-up Book media on the Knowledge of Young Women in SDN 008 Samarinda*

Statistical test results obtained knowledge variable p value = 0,000 because the value of $p < 0.05$ then the results of the bivariate test variable knowledge is that there are significant differences in the knowledge of young women about menarche before and after being given health education.

From the results of statistical tests it can be concluded that there is a significant influence on health education of menarche on the knowledge of young women in SDN 008 Samarinda Samarinda.

After getting health education with pop-up book media, there was a change in students' knowledge about menarche that was known from the results of the pre-test and post-test. According to Novita and Frasciska (2012), that health education can improve people's knowledge and understanding of health issues and can make decisions to change attitudes on the basis of health provided. This is in accordance with the goals of health education namely, changing the attitudes of individuals, groups, and communities towards positive things

in a planned manner through the learning process (Mubarak and Nurul, 2009).

One of the things that makes health education or education effective is the methods and media used. In this research, the media used are pop-up books. Pop-up book media is a book that has 3-dimensional elements and can move when the page is opened, has a beautiful and enforceable image display, provides a more interesting visualization of the story, so the learning process with pop-up book media will be much more enjoyable because the media can enlarge the interest and attention of students in the health education learning process.

This pop-up book media is presented in the form of information that is easily understood by students and attracts attention. The beginning of the introduction of the pop-up book media to the students really attracted their attention, because for them this was something new in the implementation of health education. Researchers began to open the first page of the media, visible from the expressions of students very curious about the following pages.

This is consistent with the theory of Dzuanda (2011) that the advantage of this Pop-up Book media is to provide a more interesting visualization of the story starting from the display of images that look more dimensional to images that can move when the page is opened or the parts are shifted, giving surprises in each page that can invite awe when the page is opened, reinforce the impression to be conveyed in a story and visual appearance that is more dimensional so that it makes the story feel more real.

Another study that uses Pop-up book media although it is not similar to this study is Silvia (2015) with the title "The Effect of Pop-Up Book Media Use on Narrative Writing Skills of Elementary School Students", states that there is a significant influence on the use of pop-up media book on narrative writing skills of Class III students of SDN Banjaran Driyorejo Gresik. Setywan's research (2014) also states that using Pop Up Book media can improve the speaking skills of class II students of SDN 1 Wonoharjo in the 2013/2014 school year.

The learning method used in using pop-up media is the lecture method. The advantage of the lecture method is that the place where health education activities can be organized, is easier to prepare and implement. A very appropriate method to start introducing new material and material delivered in accordance with the objectives of counseling.

Based on the results of research that has been done can prove that health education can change a person's knowledge.

V. CONCLUSION

It is known that the level of knowledge of female adolescents in SDN 008 Samarinda Seberang before being given health education about menarche is mostly in the sufficient category of 26 respondents (74.3%). The level of knowledge of female teenagers in SDN 008 Samarinda Seberang about menarche after being given health education almost all respondents in the good category that is as many as 30 respondents (85.7%). In analyzing data by conducting paired t-test, the knowledge variable shows that the p value is $0,000 < 0.05$ ($p < \alpha$). Based on the results of tests conducted, it

can be concluded that there is an influence of health education with pop-up book media about menarche on the knowledge of teenage girls in SDN 008 Samarinda Seberang in 2018.

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